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Nanosecond photoluminescence decay in zinc molybdate oxide nanocrystals observed by TCSPC and phase shift methods

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Abstract. Hydrothermally grown zinc molybdate oxide (ZMO) nanocrystals were prepared for their interesting scintillation properties at room temperature. Here we report on the comparison of two time resolved photoluminescence (PL) decay measurements of ZMO: one using time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) based on short pulse excitation and the second based on the frequency resolved phase delay between sinusoidal excitation and emission. Both methods allow PL decay to be measured with a time resolution about 1 ns. While the time resolution of the TCSPC was limited by the excitation pulse width (slightly below 1 ns), the time resolution of the phase shift method was limited by the maximum operating frequency of the conventional UV LED (3 MHz). The phase method offers a low-cost alternative to TCSPC measurements of ZnO nanorods.

1. Introduction

ZnO exhibits wide range of photoluminescence (PL) centers with mean time PL decay ranging from hundreds of ps (excitons in near UV spectral range) to microseconds (defect-related red PL) [1–3]. Their properties have been studied for decades, still producing new scientific results [4–6]. For example, the excitonic luminescence decay time was faster than 2 ns and the afterglow at 30 ns was ~0.05% in ZnO:Al ceramics [7]. In our group, we studied thermally unstable oxygen- and molybdenum-related charge trapping centers and showed that molybdenum and oxygen created in some cases electron-hole trapping pairs. Some parts of the hole trapping centers seemed to be directly connected with the creation of Mo⁵⁺ [8]. Red luminescence occurred in all Mo-doped ZnO [9]. The intensity of this band demonstrated different dependences on the annealing temperatures in the samples with different Mo content. The exciton-related UV band at 380 nm never observed in the powder samples before the annealing, appeared after the annealing at 350 °C. It was strongest in samples with low Mo content.

A spectrofluorometer to measure PL decay time based on the phase shift between sinusoidal excitation and emission was described in our previous paper [10]. The method was particularly suitable for relatively slow (μ s) PL decays observed in YAG:Er (green PL) or vacancy-related defects in ZnO (red PL). The time resolution was limited to about 10 ns due to the 100 kHz bandwidth of the lock-in amplifier. Later, better time resolution was achieved in blue spectral range when measuring a relatively strong PL signal of plasma treated recycled soda-lime glass powder [11]. The PL decay was in the order of several ns and two slow PL decay components with a mean decay time of about 8 ns and 3 μ s were

confirmed by time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) measurements. However, a relatively long lock-in integration time 10 s and low spectral resolution (8 nm) was needed to achieve a very high phase stability (typically overnight measurement for one spectrum).

While the TCSPC method is now commercially available and widely used, we developed the phase method as a low-cost student setup. Recently, we increased the maximum frequency from 100 kHz to 3 MHz. The improved setup allows PL decay to be measured with a time resolution of less than 1 ns at a reasonable time and spectral resolution (4 nm).

2. Experimental

2.1. Sample preparation

Zinc molybdate oxide (ZMO) nanocrystals were grown by hydrothermal method. The nutrient solution was prepared using 25mM of zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), 25mM of hexamethylenetetramine (HMTA, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$) and ammonium heptamolybdate tetrahydrate ($(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (NHMO)). The temperature (90°C) and the time period (3h) of growth were kept constant for all the samples. For more details see e.g.[12] and [13].

Figure 1. Photoluminescence setup: UV LED, UV fused silica biconvex lenses (L1 and L2), UV band-pass optical filter (BP), sample (S), long-pass optical filter (LP), monochromator, iris diaphragm (D), photomultiplier (PMT), Si photodiode (PD), current amplifier (CA) and lock-in amplifier (LA) with built-in sine wave generator.

2.2. Photoluminescence spectroscopy

UV-excited photoluminescence (PL) emission spectra of ZMO were measured in the 350–700 nm spectral range using commercial pulsed UV light emitting diode (LED) #XSL-360-5E (Roither Lasertechnik, GmbH, Vienna, Austria, wavelength 360 nm, output power 1 mW) operating in ac mode, a narrow band pass optical filter BP360 (Thorlabs #FBH360-10 transparent in 350–370 nm spectra range), long pass optical filter LP375 (Edmund Optics #34-302 transparent above 375 nm), a monochromator (Horiba H20VIS, spectral range 300-800 nm, spectral resolution 4 nm), a red-sensitive

photomultiplier (Photonis #XP2203B, spectral range 300-760 nm) and a 50 MHz lock-in amplifier (Zurich Instruments HF2LI), see figure 1. Biased sine modulated power for the UV LED was provided directly by HF2LI via built-in sine-wave generator. PMT photocurrent was converted to voltage signal by current amplifier (Zurich Instruments HF2TA). The setup was spectrally calibrated with a calibrated halogen lamp (Oriental Instruments #63358).

For comparison, the time-correlated single-photon counting setup (TCSPC) was used to measure time resolved PL of $Zn_xMo_{1-x}O$. The setup is built on nanosecond nanoLED pulsed light excitation source (Horiba Scientific, Piscataway, NJ, USA) equipped with a spectrofluorometer 5000 M (Horiba Jobin Yvon, Wildwood, MA, USA), a single-grating monochromator and a photon-counting detector TBX-04 (Hamamatsu, Photonics, Hamamatsu City, Shizuoka, Japan). The PL decay times were fitted using convolution procedure included in commercial software (SpectraSolve software package 3.01 PRO, Ames Photonics, Fort Worth, TX, USA).

3. Theoretical

The phase delay method is based on a phase shift between the sine wave excitation and emission signals. In the case of the mono-exponential decay $PL(t) \sim e^{-t/\tau}$, the phase delay $\Delta\phi$ (in degrees) between the sine wave excitation and emission at the frequency f (in Hz) is directly related to the mean decay time τ via the formula [14]

$$2\pi f \tau = \tan \Delta\phi \quad (1)$$

Since the phase resolution in our setup is about 0.1° , the Eq. (1) implies the time resolution of about 1 ns at 1 MHz frequency. If the PL decay is not mono exponential, the Eq. (1) gives only a mean time of PL decay which depends on frequency and the frequency resolved phase shift between the excitation and emission needs to be measured [14]. This is because at low frequency the slow processes dominate the PL signal, whereas at high frequency the fast ones. Therefore, it is important to measure the phase shift separately at each selected wavelength in a broad frequency range. To eliminate the phase shift caused by the setup ("instrumental error"), the phase shift was measured at the excitation wavelength 360 nm and subtracted (a reference signal).

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the PL intensity, and the mean time of PL decay spectra of ZMO measured at 1 MHz at room temperature. The PL decay time is very short, especially in the blue spectral region, with a PL mean time decay of a few ns, increasing to 10 ns in the red spectral region, as expected for dipole radiation, where the classical expression for the total power radiated by an oscillating dipole increases with the fourth power of the frequency [15]. Therefore, the number of quanta per second emitted by the dipole (transition probability) increases with the cube of the frequency, and the mean decay time decreases with photon energy (increases with wavelength), as observed in figure 2. The phase shift between the excitation and emission signal measured as a function of frequency at selected wavelengths, shown in figure 3, is very small at frequencies below 100 kHz. Only at about 1 MHz is the phase shift larger than 1° as expected for fast PL decay. Note that the noise in the phase shift frequency spectra at wavelengths above 600 nm is due to low PL intensity, see figure 2.

Figure 2. The spectrally resolved PL intensity (blue) of ZMO and the mean PL decay time (red), including errorbars, measured using sine wave UV excitation at 1 MHz at room temperature.

Figure 3. The frequency spectra of phase shifts of the ac PL signal of ZMO at various emission wavelengths relative to the reference signal at the excitation wavelength 360 nm (subtracted at each frequency from the measured phase shift). All measurements were done at room temperature.

The TCSPC confirms the fast (ns) time resolved PL decay, see figure 4. The fitted curve of TCSPC data reveals also a slow PL decay component with the time constant about 20 ns. The data were fitted using the formula

$$I(t) = A_0 + \sum_{i=1}^2 A_i e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}}$$

where $A_0=3.37$, $A_1=1103$, $\tau_1=2.6$ ns, $A_2=68$ and $\tau_2=19.4$ ns.

Figure 4. The time resolved PL emission of ZMO measured by TCSPC at 500 nm with 340 nm excitation and 1 ns pulse. The instrumental response function measured at the excitation pulse wavelength (excitation pulse shape) and fitted curve were added for comparison. All measurements were done at room temperature.

The comparison of Figure 2 and Figure 4 shows that the phase method measures mainly the fast component of the PL decay at high frequency. In our case, the 4 ns mean PL decay time was measured at 500 nm wavelength by the phase method at 1 MHz frequency compared to 2.6 ns evaluated by TCSPC.

5. Conclusions

Hydrothermally grown, pellet-pressed ZMO nanocrystals were investigated for time-resolved visible photoluminescence at room temperature under UV excitation. Two optical setups were compared. The TCSPC setup was based on ns-short-pulse excitation followed by time resolved histogram-like counting of emitted photons. The phase method, based on the frequency-resolved phase delay between sinusoidal excitation and emission, offers a low-cost alternative to TCSPC measurements of ZMO. Both methods gave a similar time resolution in the order of 1 ns. While the time resolution of the TCSPC was limited by the excitation pulse width (about 1 ns), the time resolution of the phase shift method was limited by the maximum operating frequency of the UV LED (about 3 MHz).

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